
"Doppler Redshift" Explanation of the Source of Energy in the Universe's Expansion—Explanation of cosmic expansion without dark energy

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Abstract: The mainstream explanation for the expansion of the universe still centers on dark energy, but it is puzzling that we have not found dark energy in experiments so far. Through the re-analysis of the cosmic background radiation, this paper hopes to prove theoretically that the energy of our cosmic expansion comes from the matter itself, and the main source of energy is the Doppler redshift effect of electromagnetic radiation. Through theoretical analysis, we have proved that it is not so much that gravity is preventing the expansion of the universe, but that gravity is promoting the accelerated expansion of our universe.

At the same time, we give a mechanism of entropy decrease contrary to the second law of thermodynamics, and our universe does not go to heat death during the expansion stage, but to cold death.

Keywords: cosmic expansion, Doppler redshift, second law of thermodynamics, entropy decrease

1 Introduction

The author is not professional in astronomy, but based on the basic theory of physics, he tries to answer the following important theoretical questions in astronomy in this article:

1) Dark energy does not exist in our universe, and energy conservation has always been strictly observed in our universe. The source of energy for the expansion of the universe is the energy released by the accumulation of matter itself under the action of gravity, and the energy released by nuclear fusion under the action of gravity.

2) The expansion of the universe is mainly due to the relativistic Doppler redshift effect, and the microwave background radiation is not caused by the expansion of the universe. The microwave background radiation experiences a severe Doppler redshift effect in the beginning of the expansion process of the universe, which provides an important source of energy for the initial stage of cosmic expansion.

3) Our universe releases huge amounts of energy (generated by gravity and nuclear fusion) during the formation of galaxies, and eventually releases it into space through Doppler redshift, accelerating the expansion of the universe.

2 Explanation of the expansion of the universe

2.1 The Early Expansion of the Universe and the Microwave Background Radiation

We have argued in another article that "space is relatively independent" conclusion^[1], our universe will not stretch the wavelength of photons for no reason in the process of expansion, otherwise the universe will fall into the dilemma of energy conservation.

Therefore, from the theory of physics, we are almost sure that the cosmic microwave background radiation does not come from the elongation of photon wavelength in the process of cosmic expansion, but from the Doppler redshift effect caused by the reflection of photons back and forth in the early expansion of the universe, which provides an important energy source for the early expansion of our universe.

As shown in Figure 1 below:

Fig. 1 Doppler redshift effect

We assume that A and B are two smooth mirrors, A and B move away from each other at the speed V , and the initial frequency is ω of photons reflected back and forth between a and B. According to the Doppler frequency shift formula:

$$\omega_{k+1} = \omega_k \cdot \sqrt{\frac{c - v}{c + v}}$$

Once a photon is reflected, its frequency is reduced. Therefore, we can infer that after n reflections, the frequency of the photon will become very low, and we can assume that the frequency of the photon will become ω_n . According to the conservation of energy, we know that the energy lost by Doppler redshift of photons will be converted into kinetic energy between objects A and B:

$$h(\omega - \omega_n) = \frac{1}{2}(m_A + m_B) \cdot (v_1^2 - v^2)$$

Where, m_A and m_B are the static masses of objects A and B, respectively; v_1 is the relative velocity of motion of objects A and B after absorbing the Doppler red-shifted energy of the photon, v is the initial velocity of motion of objects A and B.

Therefore, in fact, during the expansion of our universe, every time a photon is reflected (or first absorbed and then emitted again), part of its energy is converted into kinetic energy of relative motion between matter.

The blackbody distribution characteristics of microwave background radiation further illustrate that in the early stage of universe expansion^[2], our universe is like an opaque blackbody in a rapidly expanding state. Photons are constantly reflected in this expanding blackbody. Through the Doppler red shift effect, most of the energy is transformed into kinetic energy of matter moving away from each other, providing the initial energy source for universe expansion.

2.2 Stages of Deceleration before Galaxies Form in Large Numbers

According to the Big Bang theory, if the expansion energy of the universe comes from the Doppler shift effect caused by the light emitted by the matter itself, our universe will experience a deceleration stage from the beginning of the universe to the formation of a large number of galaxies.

Because the energy of the initial photons in the rapidly expanding universe gradually decreases after the Doppler redshift effect, and the efficiency of absorption and reflection of photons decreases as the universe expands.

Therefore, at this stage, the universe is doing work against gravity, and the expansion speed will naturally decrease gradually.

2.3 Phase of accelerated expansion during the epoch of massive formation of galaxies

We take a simple model as an example, as shown in Figure 2 below:

Fig. 2 Local gravitational contraction of the universe

We assume that A, B, C and D are four planets, the initial distance is R , and the static mass is m ; Attract by gravity, that distance of A and B, and the distance of C and D all become R_1 , the distance of B and C increases to $2R - R_1$.

The gravitational potential energy between them before the merger is:

$$E_{AB}^R = E_{BC}^R = E_{CD}^R = -G \frac{m \cdot m}{R}$$

$$E_{AC}^{2R} = E_{BD}^{2R} = -G \frac{m \cdot m}{2R}$$

$$E_{AD}^{3R} = -G \frac{m \cdot m}{3R}$$

The gravitational potential energy after the merger is:

$$E_{AB}^{R_1} = E_{CD}^{R_1} = -G \frac{m \cdot m}{R_1}$$

$$E_{AC}^{2R} = E_{BD}^{2R} = -G \frac{m \cdot m}{2R}$$

$$E_{BC}^{2R-R_1} = -G \frac{m \cdot m}{2R - R_1}$$

$$E_{AD}^{2R+R_1} = -G \frac{m \cdot m}{2R + R_1}$$

We can easily show that when R_1 is small enough, the mass of matter under

gravity releases huge amounts of energy. Most of the energy released by the accumulation of matter in the universe will eventually be converted into electromagnetic waves and radiated out. And the above model is very suitable for the situation of our current universe.

In our universe, matter gathers to form galaxies because of gravity, which will produce huge gravitational potential energy, and the energy generated by this gravity will be released into space in the form of electromagnetic radiation generated by the thermal motion of matter.

At the same time, the formation of stars will also produce huge energy due to nuclear fusion, which will also radiate huge energy in the form of electromagnetic radiation.

All this radiation energy travels back and forth in our cosmic space, producing a Doppler redshift effect, and eventually the energy is converted into kinetic energy for galaxies to move away from each other. At this stage, our universe begins to accelerate again.

2.4 With the expansion of the universe, the future universe will usher in a deceleration phase

From the point of view of cosmic isotropy, we can assume that the universe is a sphere with accelerating expansion. There are two formulas as follows:

1) The formula of gravitational potential energy (in the case of long-distance expansion):

$$E_p = -\frac{GMm}{r}$$

2) Volume formula:

$$V = \frac{4\pi R^3}{3}$$

When the average distance of cosmic celestial bodies (galaxies or galaxy clusters) doubles, the energy density of radiation in the entire cosmic vacuum will become 1/8 of the original due to the 8-fold increase in volume; the radiation energy obtained by galaxies per unit time will be It is reduced to 1/8 of the original; but assuming that the speed of the celestial bodies moving away from each other remains unchanged, the negative work done by the gravitational potential energy between the celestial bodies in unit time due to expansion will only become 1/2 of the original.

Therefore, if the speed of photons produced by stars in our universe remains unchanged or gradually decreases, then with the continuous expansion of the universe, the energy density of photons in the universe will eventually be lower than a certain value, so that the energy obtained by celestial bodies from Doppler effect is less than the negative work done by gravitational potential energy, and the universe will become a decelerating expansion stage.

Therefore, our universe may be in the process of continuous expansion and

contraction.

The entire energy cycle of the universe may be as follows:

2.5 Search for the evidence that the expansion energy of the universe comes from the Doppler redshift

New galaxies will produce a large number of stars and radiate energy to the outside world. Because galaxies radiate a large amount of electromagnetic radiation, they will accelerate. This motion will be accelerated in the brightest period of galaxies. We should be able to observe the acceleration effect of galaxies at this stage.

3 Our universe will go cold during the expansion phase

According to the second law of thermodynamics:

$$dQ \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right) = dS < 0$$

In the current laws of thermodynamics, we think that the universe is in the process of entropy increase. However, in fact, the underlying assumptions of this formula are:

- 1) Heat in an object always exists in the form of kinetic energy of molecules and atoms;
- 2) Conservation of energy in an isolated system;
- 3) This energy exists unchanged in the form of the kinetic energy of the molecule.

However, we can also construct such an isolated system, as shown in Figure 3 below: A and B are a sealed device with hot gas inside; A、B and the pipeline are floating in space, the pipeline is almost adiabatic to the outside and infinitely long, and the interior is A smooth plane that completely reflects photons, A and B are filled with a lot of hot gas, and their heat exchange is done by radiating photons between each other. Both A and B have initial velocity v .

Fig. 3 Conversion of thermal energy into kinetic energy of an object

So according to our analysis above, if the energy is conserved and remains in this isolated system, the final radiated photon energy will all be converted into the kinetic energy of A and B through the Doppler redshift effect (we assume that there is no energy spillover and friction effect), and the whole system will become a lonely and cold two objects a and B moving away from each other.

For the whole universe, at least we observe that the present universe is in the stage where this "atomic kinetic energy" is converted into the movement of stars away from each other, which does not actually conform to the second law of thermodynamics. In this process, our universe is entropy decreasing as a whole.

4 Conclusion

Combining with another paper of the author, we first demonstrate that due to the

relative independence of space, in fact, the real source of the cosmic microwave background radiation is the Doppler redshift effect, and it is the microwave background radiation that provides an important energy source for the expansion of our universe in the early stage.

In the formation stage of a large number of galaxies in our universe, the local gravitational energy and nuclear fusion energy in the process of galaxy formation provide the energy source for the second accelerated expansion of our universe, which is also the Doppler redshift effect. Therefore, it is not so much that gravity is preventing our universe from expanding as that gravity itself is promoting the expansion of our universe.

To prove the idea proposed in this paper, we can observe the accelerated expansion effect of newborn galaxies, which will accelerate the expansion speed of these galaxies relative to other galaxies due to the increase of external radiation energy during the birth process of newborn galaxies.

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